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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Antibacterial Effect of Graphene-Collagen Nanocomposites on *Salmonella* species

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this report is to summarize the applicability of nanocomposites against clinically significant pathogen *Salmonella enterica serotype holeraesius*. The antibacterial effect of single SiO₂/RGO nanoparticles and combination of Ag decorated RGO, SiO₂/RGO and ZnTiO were examined. ZnTiO nanoparticles were prepared using nonhydrolytic sol-gel method. The various nanoparticles combinations were evaluated, dispersed in type I fibrillary collagen gel with concentration of 2.64 w% in different ratios with nanoparticles. The lyophilization process was used to prepare nanocomposite material. Several nanocomposites as Coll: RGO, Coll: Ag/RGO, Ag/ SiO₂/RGO, ZnTiO / SiO₂/RGO, Coll: ZnTiO were tested on *S. enterica*. The formed sterile zones around the disc samples (diameter of 9.0 mm, thickness of 3 mm) were measured in mm (± 0.5). Some of the tested materials have shown antibacterial activity on *S. enterica* but the other have no effect. The research team relies on an innovative combination of qualities of different nanoparticles which aims synergy and high antibacterial activity with potential application in medical practice.

Introduction

Salmonella is known as clinically and socially significant microorganism causing damages of animal and human's health. Also it causes an enormous loss in the food industry.

Salmonella spp. is found to be infectious for livestock and humans and cause significant public health problems worldwide [1]. The appearance of severe infections, caused by *Salmonella spp.* due to its ability of biofilm formation in food manufacturing and processing plants, is reported by Murray, et al. [2]. The nanobiotechnology is applicable at any stage of the fight against *Salmonella* including identification and diagnostics [3], drug delivery [4], increasing the efficiency of conventional antibiotics [5], and their own antibacterial ability in a single application [1,6,7]. A lot of *Salmonella* strains isolated from animal stocks are resistant to one or three classes of antibiotics [8]. Many types of nanoparticles and nanocomposites gives promising results on antibacterial effect. It should be taken into account that some *Salmonella* strains have strong defense against silver nanoparticles [9]

Nanoparticles are promising material for drug delivery, as they are able to adsorb and/or encapsulate a drug, this ways protecting it against chemical and enzymatic degradation. Owing to their nature, nanoparticles are more stable than liposomes in biological fluids and during storage. Nanocapsules are vesicular systems in which

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the drug is confined to a cavity surrounded by a unique polymer membrane, while nanospheres are matrix systems in which the drug is physically and uniformly dispersed [10]. One of the problems with antibiotic loaded nanoparticles is that in some cases the capacity of a polymeric drug carrier should be engineered to incorporate high concentrations of antibiotics to achieve the required dosage, yet avoid side effects that may be associated with higher amounts of carriers. This seems a difficult task, however, Ranjan, et al. [11] introduced two novel technologies by which high concentrations of gentamicin could be incorporated into the nanocomposites. He enhanced antibacterial efficacy of gentamicin using a core-shell nanostructures approach. Nanostructures administered *in vivo* either at multiple dosage of $5 \mu\text{g}^{-1}$ or single dosage of $15 \mu\text{g}^{-1}$ in AJ-646 mice infected with *Salmonella* resulted in significant reduction of viable bacteria in the liver and spleen. Histopathological evaluation for concentration-dependent toxicity at a dosage of $15 \mu\text{g}^{-1}$ revealed mineralized deposits in 50% kidney tissues of free gentamicin-treated mice, which in contrast was absent in nanostructure-treated mice. Thus, encapsulation of gentamicin in nanostructures may reduce toxicity and improve *in vivo* bacterial clearance [12].

The results have shown that, the combination of antibiotics and metal nanoparticles could increase the antibiotic efficacy against resistant pathogens. Nanoparticle - antibiotic conjugates lower the amount of both agents in the concentration, which reduces harmfulness and increases antimicrobial properties. These conjugates were effective against resistant bacteria species due to the fact, that the concentrations of antibiotics were increased at the place of antibiotic -microbe interaction and thus accelerate the binding between microbes and antibiotics [13].

Biologically obtained silver nanoparticles enhanced the antibacterial activity of the antibiotics in a synergistic mode on *Salmonella* pathogens. In both the cases the highest zone of inhibition of *S. typhi* and *S. paratyphi* was found in the combination of ofloxacin + silver NPs followed by ceftriaxone + silver NPs, ofloxacin, ceftiaxone and silver NPs [5]. Rodrigues, et al. [14] and Sanguinèdo [15] reported the antibacterial effect of fungal synthesized silver nanoparticles.

The study on the antibacterial activity, biofilm formation and their primary adherence capacity of both the species of *Salmonella* (*Salmonella typhi* and *Salmonella paratyphi*) proved of the prospective of the nanoparticles as antimicrobial agents [16]. Antibacterial nanomaterials possess the ability to inhibit the growth of the bacteria; hence, they could be effectively used in biomedical devices, biomechanics, and tissue engineering applications [17]. Usually, the antibacterial nanomaterials are applied to inhibit bacterial infection in implanted medical devices, since the bacterial infection can cause device failure and tissue inflammation [18]. Conventionally, silver nanoparticles are being used

as antibacterial materials in biomedical devices; however, they have certain drawbacks such as high cost, toxicity to the environment, and problems in disposal of the wastes [19]. Recently, graphene and its derivatives have attracted increasing attention in preparing antibacterial materials owing to their excellent antibacterial activities against bacteria [20,21]. However, large surface area and strong Van der Waals force among the graphene sheets make significant agglomeration in the polymer matrix and this hamper their practical applications [22,23]. Furthermore, the aromatic nature of the C-C bond of the graphene makes them chemically stable and inert [24]. These drawbacks could be overcome by using functionalized graphenes, particularly Graphene Oxide (GO) and Reduced Graphene Oxide (RGO), which possesses oxygen functionalities (carboxyl, hydroxyl and epoxy groups) and is well dispersed in water and some organic solvents [25,26].

Collagen-based biomaterials with antimicrobial activity are attractive candidates for wound dressing, tissue engineering, components of implantable devices, etc. One of the easiest and most effective ways among the large variety of known approaches to add antimicrobial activity of biomaterials is development of composites including antimicrobial agents.

Many antimicrobial compounds and nanoparticles are known whose activity is often associated with the presence of metal ions, such as silver-, zinc-, titanium- and other as well as of some nanoparticles. For example, metal oxide nanoparticles (including ZnO and TiO₂) were reported to affect the bacterial communities and the associated processes through effects on susceptible, narrow-function bacterial taxa [27].

ZnO is among compounds that are currently listed as Generally Recognized as Safe (GRAS) by the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (21CFR182.8991). The inhibitory effect of ZnO nanoparticles against *Salmonella* was dependent on the concentration of ZnO. After initial killing of cells by ZnO treatment, the cell populations of *Salmonella* remained constant during the 8 d incubation with the numbers of cells after 8 d at 5.10^5 CFU/mL for 0.28 mg/mL. In the 1.12 mg/mL solution, *Salmonella* cells decreased to 10^3 CFU/mL, whereas the control grew to 10^{10} CFU/mL [28].

Materials and Methods

Preparation and characterization of RGO was conducted as described earlier by Stoyanova, et al. [29]. Fibrillar collagen/antimicrobial agent porous hybrids were prepared by adsorption of the antimicrobial agent from suspension during the fabrication of a porous collagen matrix as described by Albu, et al. [30]. ZnTiO₃ in form of crystal powder with particles size of about 8 nm was used in this study as a new antimicrobial agent. A known nonhydrolytic sol-gel method was used for its preparation [31]. Briefly,

zinc acetate (Sigma-Aldrich) and titanium ethoxide (Fluka AG) were used as starting materials.

The obtained collagen/ZnTiO₃ and collagen/RGO impregnated with Ag and SiO₂ nanoparticles was prepared as described by Abu, et al. [32], Abu & Ghica [33].

The test microbial strains (*Salmonella enterica* serotype choleraesuis) for this study were provided by the National Bank of Microorganisms and Cell Cultures (NBIMCC), Bulgaria. *Salmonella* strains were grown in Nutrient Broth (NB) at 180 rpm for 18 h (NA, Conda, Spain) at 37°C. Microbial density of 0.5 was determined according to McFarland. The aliquots of 100 µl microbial suspension were randomly spread on a solid medium (NA), and discs of the investigated material were put on them. The plates were left for 20 h at 4–6°C to afford diffusion of the nanoparticles and, after that, were incubated for 24 h at 37°C. The formed sterile zones around the disc samples (diameter of 9.0 mm; thickness of 3 mm) were measured in mm (± 0.5). RGO and Ag/RGO dispersions in different ratios were sonicated by “Bandelin” sonicator (Germany). A small quantity of nanomaterials dispersions were dropped (10 µl) on the inoculated Petri dishes. After that the plates were left for 20 h at 4–6°C and then were cultivated for 24 h at 37°C. The formed sterile zone were measured and mean value presented in tables. All experiments were performed in triplicate and the results were statistically processed using standard mathematical operations.

The nanocomposite of collagen and graphene have potential in implant surgery as demonstrated by Istrate, et al. [34]. The ratio of collagen/nanocomposites’ compounds were different for Coll: RGO; Coll: Ag/RGO; Ag/SiO₂/RGO and ZnTiO₃/SiO₂/RGO respectively.

Results

The antimicrobial activity, as a sterile zone in mm, of the studied nanocomposites was presented.

There was no effect on the growth and development of the test bacteria in presence of Coll: graphene oxide and lack of free sharp edges in the collagen matrix, resulting a lack of antibacterial effect against tested microorganisms. The lack of concentration dependent toxic effect on Gram-negative bacteria like *Salmonella* spp. could be due not only to its small size but to the packaging of bacterial cells in the space between RGO sheets. During the interaction with bacteria the orientation of graphene oxide sheets is very important [20]. In this case the nanocomposite is included in collagen matrix and some of the free edges are not in the direct contact with bacteria.

Nanocomposite Coll: Ag/RGO has shown a little bit stronger effect against *S. enterica* only at the highest ratio 2:1 (1.25 mm sterile zone). The results are shown in table 1.

The nanocomposite Ag/SiO₂/RGO in different ratios with collagen porous material has showed antibacterial effect against *S. enterica*. Zone of the growth inhibition can be seen at table 2.

All tested concentrations Ag/SiO₂/RGO on *S. enterica* have weak or insignificant effect, but stronger than Coll: Ag/RGO nanocomposite. Stronger effect of Ag/SiO₂/RGO is possibly due to the role of SiO₂ as dispersing agent (vehiculum). It is interesting that SiO₂ alone as nano size powder has no antibacterial effect.

In table 3 are shown the data for bacterial growth inhibition in presence of Collagen: ZnTiO₃.

Against Gracilicutes bacteria like *Salmonella enterica* Coll: Ag/ZnO/ZnTiO₃ nanocomposite demonstrated weak inhibition effect, but strongest at highest concentration ratio (2:1) as can be seen in table 4.

The nanocomposite ZnTiO₃ / SiO₂/RGO demonstrated the strongest antimicrobial effect³ against *S. enterica*. The sterile zones which were measured are shown in table 5. The zone of inhibition size of obtained nanocomposites Coll: ZnTiO₃ / SiO₂/RGO depend on the concentration. For *S. enterica* the best inhibition effect was observed at ratio 2:1 of Coll: ZnTiO₃ / SiO₂/RGO. Obviously this combination with Coll: ZnTiO₃ / SiO₂/RGO possessed the best antimicrobial effect. It is worth

Table 1: Antibacterial effect of nanocomposite Ag/RGO in different weight ratio with collagen matrix.

Antibacterial Agent (weight ratio)	Zone of Inhibition (mm)
Coll:Ag/RGO (2:1)	0.25 ± 0.1
Coll:Ag/RGO (2:0.8)	0
Coll:Ag/RGO (2:0.7)	0
Coll:Ag/RGO (2:0.6)	0

Table 2: Antibacterial effect of nanocomposite Ag/SiO₂/RGO in different weight ratio with collagen matrix.

Antibacterial Agent (weight ratio)	Zone of Inhibition (mm)
Coll: Ag/SiO ₂ /RGO (2:1)	1.8 ± 0.5
Coll: Ag/SiO ₂ /RGO (2:0.8)	1.75 ± 0.5
Coll: Ag/SiO ₂ /RGO (2:0.6)	1.5 ± 0.5
Coll: Ag/SiO ₂ /RGO (2:0.4)	0.875 ± 0.2

Table 3: Antibacterial effect of nanocomposite ZnTiO₃ in different weight ratio with collagen matrix.

Antibacterial Agent (weight ratio)	Zone of Inhibition (mm)
Coll: ZnTiO ₃ (2:1)	6.6 ± 0.5
Coll: ZnTiO ₃ (2:0.8)	4.5 ± 0.5
Coll: ZnTiO ₃ (2:0.6)	2.5 ± 0.5
Coll: ZnTiO ₃ (2:0.4)	1.5 ± 0.5
Coll:ZnTiO ₃ (2:0.2)	1.5 ± 0.5

Table 4: Antibacterial effect of nanocomposite Ag/ZnO/ZnTiO₃ in different weight ratio with collagen matrix.

Antibacterial Agent (weight ratio)	Zone of Inhibition (mm)
Coll:Ag/ZnO/ZnTiO ₃ (2:1)	1.25 ± 0.5
Coll:Ag/ZnO/ZnTiO ₃ (2:0.8)	0.75 ± 0.5
Coll:Ag/ZnO/ZnTiO ₃ (2:0.6)	0.5 ± 0.2
Coll:Ag/ZnO/ZnTiO ₃ (2:0.4)	0

Table 5: Antibacterial effect of nanocomposite ZnTiO₃/SiO₂/RGO in different weight ratio with collagen matrix.

Antibacterial Agent (weight ratio)	Zone of Inhibition (mm)
Coll: ZnTiO ₃ /SiO ₂ /RGO (2:1)	10.0 ± 0.5
Coll: ZnTiO ₃ /SiO ₂ /RGO (2:0.8)	9.75 ± 0.5
Coll: ZnTiO ₃ /SiO ₂ /RGO (2:0.6)	6.0 ± 0.5
Coll: ZnTiO ₃ /SiO ₂ /RGO (2:0.4)	2.5 ± 0.5
Coll: ZnTiO ₃ /SiO ₂ /RGO (2:0.2)	0

to mention that ZnTiO₃ alone as nano size powder has less effect on the tested bacterial strain.

RGO and Ag/RGO nanoparticles have no effect on *S.choleraesuis*.

Discussion

One of the antimicrobial agent used in this study was crystalline ZnTiO₃ with particles size of about 8 nm, containing around 13% amorphous phase most probably consisting mainly of ZnO and TiO₂. The sharp shape and small size of the ZnTiO₃ nano crystals (of about 8 nm) are prerequisites, characteristic of nanoparticles highly active to prokaryotic cells [35-37]. ZnTiO₃ was entrapped in a porous collagen matrix by sol-gel cryogen drying to preserve the native biological activity of the collagen. No chemical interactions were expected in the Collagen/ZnTiO₃ nanocomposites under these conditions. Their biological activity could be due to the presence of very small cubic ZnTiO₃ nanocrystals, amorphous phase consisting presumably by ZnO and TiO₂ particles and the assisting action of the collagen matrix. Unfortunately, the ZnTiO₃ mechanism of biological activity was not studied up to now and that of ZnO and TiO₂ is still not fully understood.

Based on the knowledge up to date, three mechanisms of action could be supposed for the antimicrobial activity of the Collagen/ZnTiO₃ nanocomposites: i) mechanical demolition of the cell wall and membrane by nanoparticles entrapped in the collagen matrix; ii) Collagen/ZnTiO₃ nanocomposites metal ions chelation and iii) formation of free oxygen radicals due to interactions between microbial environment and the metal oxide nanoparticles.

Both the crystal phase (cubic ZnTiO₃) and small amount amorphous phase of the used antimicrobial agent entrapped in the collagen matrix, probably cause a mechanical

demolition of the cell envelope and membrane in a way similar to that earlier reported for titanium-doped ZnO on *E. coli* and *Staphylococcus* sp., visualized by SEM observation [38]. Chelation of Collagen/ZnTiO₃ nanocomposite metals could also contribute to its biological activity. It is possible also for free electron couples of oxygen and nitrogen atoms of the peptide bonds to chelate with the ZnO and TiO₂ presenting as amorphous phase of the antimicrobial agent. The negative charge (under the test conditions) of the microbial cell wall could be a reason for intake of the metal ions entrapped in the collagen molecules. In sufficiently high concentrations, metal ions engulfed in the cells cause toxicity to any cells [39,40].

Formation of free oxygen radicals (reactive oxygen species) due to interaction between the water environment of the microbial cells and the antimicrobial agent can stipulate damages of all macromolecules in a way described by Sirelkhatim, et al. [41].

Further studies to clarify how to combine the action of different nanomaterials and other chemical agents to overcome this bacterial defending mechanisms should be conducted. It would be better if nanocomposites could be obtained by green synthesis of nanoparticles to reduce environmental risk. Also when comparing the examined nanomaterials those with very low levels of MIC and MBC, could be a priority in future research.

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